

PRE-NORMATIVE RESEARCH ON HYDROGEN RELEASES ASSESSMENT

D1.3

First version of the priority list of archetypes

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D1.3 reports the results of the activities performed by the NHyRA Consortium in Task 1.3.

In recent years, the research community has been investigating to find an answer to the potential indirect impact of H₂ on climate change. However, validated data are needed to provide a definitive answer on this topic. As shown in deliverable D1.1, many archetypes of technologies and plants are present in the H₂ supply chains. Furthermore, several plants' configurations and technologies can be implemented in each archetype, increasing the complexity and the number of potential emission sources that should be investigated. As indicated in the project proposal, choices must be made as to which archetypes and sources of H₂ emissions should be focused on since resources are usually limited. Therefore, a priority ranking of the archetypes identified in deliverable D1.1 to be investigated is suggested. Some attempts to cover the gaps have been already present in the literature. For example, Copper et al. (2022) conducted a literature review and reported preliminary emission ranges for hydrogen, indicating that green hydrogen may, in certain instances, exhibit higher emissions than blue hydrogen. However, the Authors acknowledged that these findings are subject to a high degree of uncertainty and limited reliability. Consequently, further research is required to enhance the robustness of these estimates.

Several approaches are available to provide such a priority ranking. In this work the Analytic Hierarchy Procedure (AHP) method, a ranking prioritization methodology, was adopted, developed and implemented. Six criteria have been identified for the purpose as defined in chapter 4.1: i) existence and/or uncertainty of data about H₂ emission in the state of the art; ii) total amount of H₂ emission; iii) market penetration (present and future expected potential); iv) archetype to be tested: availability, operational history, and variety of scenarios; v) availability of measurement instruments and methods; vi) cost and time for testing.

Then, a weight for each criterion was proposed according to the experts' inputs and by organizing dedicated face-to-face discussions among the partners of the NHyRA consortium. Following the discussion on the preliminary results of the criteria weighting, it was decided to limit the pairwise comparison of the archetypes to three criteria (existence and/or uncertainty of data about H₂ emission in the state of the art, total amount of H₂ emission, market penetration (present and future expected potential)), while it was suggested to use the remaining three for the reality check, i.e., to evaluate the feasibility of the testing activities.

As a result of this activity some preliminary recommendations can be given. Different opinions appear during the discussion making challenging to reach a consensus without any further data elaboration and aggregation. Based on the aggregation, the total amount of hydrogen emission into the atmosphere is considered the most relevant criteria for prioritization. Otherwise, the remaining two criteria received a similar score. Focusing to the archetypes indicated in the deliverable D1.1 (Figure 1), preliminary recommendations can be given. First, archetypes transporting and storing fluids different from H₂ in the supply chain can be neglected in the present prioritization since no direct H₂ emissions are expected. Second, also low TRL technologies should be excluded since it is foreseen that further technological advancements are expected before these technologies enter the market. Third, few data are available for some archetypes (industrial end-users and electricity generation).

Therefore, it was preferred to postpone the prioritization of these two categories when more information on all the archetypes will be available. For the remaining archetypes, the results of the prioritization are schematically shown in Figure 2 - Figure 6.

Figure 1. Archetypes identified in deliverable D1.1 that are prioritized in the present analysis.

Figure 2. Priority for H₂ production archetypes included in the analysis.

Figure 3. Priority for H2 conversion archetypes included in the analysis.

Figure 4. Priority for H2 transport archetypes included in the analysis.

Figure 5. Priority for H2 transport archetypes included in the analysis.

Figure 6. Priority for H2 end-uses archetypes in thermal purposes and mobility (ICE = Internal combustion engine; HRS = Hydrogen refuelling station). Due to the limited information on the performance of H2 technologies in industrial and energy generation archetypes, it was preferred to not indicate a priority for the alternatives.

Acronyms

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AIJ	Aggregation of Individual Judgments
AIP	Aggregation of Individual Priorities
HRS	Hydrogen Refuelling Station
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
LFA	Loss Function Approach
LOHC	Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers
MCDM	Multiple-criteria decision-making
OM	Outranking Methods
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
WAMM	Weighted Arithmetic Mean Method
WGMM	Weighted Geometric Mean Method

Symbols

A	Comparative matrix
$a_{i,j}$	Comparison between the row element a_i and the column element a_j
$b_{i,j}$	Individual judgments of the group members
B_i	i -th alternative
CI	Consistency Index
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CR	Consistency Ratio
CW	Comparative Weight
H ₂	Hydrogen
MeOH	Methanol
n	Number of alternatives
NH ₃	Ammonia
$p^r(B_i)$	Priority of the r -th participant for the alternative B_i
R	Total number of participants
RI	Random Index
RW	Relative Weight
v	Eigenvector of the comparative matrix A
w^r	Weight of each group member
λ_{\max}	Eigenvalue of the comparative matrix A

1. Introduction

Many researchers are investigating the role of H₂ emissions, its potential effect on other gases, such as methane, and its indirect contribution to climate change. Specifically, some Authors have contributed to the state-of-the-art with preliminary considerations on H₂ GWP (Warwick et al., 2022; Derwent, 2023; Chen et al., 2024; Lakshmanan & Bhati, 2024; Sand et al., 2024). Recently, other authors focused on providing some scenario analysis based on rough emissions estimates in the H₂ supply chain (Bertagni et al., 2022; Warwick et al., 2023). However, these estimations are usually characterized by relevant uncertainty due to the limited information about the topic.

Consistent data are needed to sentence and provide estimations of H₂ emissions through the value chain. As shown in deliverable D1.1 of the NHyRA project, H₂ supply chains from production to the final uses can be configured in various modes, including archetypes characterized by different operating conditions. However, testing all the possible archetypes under various conditions would not be feasible for the NHyRA Consortium in WP3 and beyond the project's scope.

Nevertheless, since the research community and industrial stakeholders will be asked to contribute to solving this knowledge gap, recommendations on testing priorities are essential.

Determining priorities is a challenging task, especially when several participants are asked to contribute to the discussion and when the available quantitative data are limited. The preliminary list of the priorities described in this deliverable has been obtained by circumscribing the analysis to the partners of the NHyRA consortium. Since the list has been determined based on the available state-of-the-art knowledge and qualitative considerations, it will be updated at the end of the project based on new knowledge based on quantitative data and, possibly, feedback from the Stakeholders Advisory Board.

2. Basic information on multicriteria methods

Multiple-criteria decision-making (MCDM) provides analytical tools to tackle complex problems characterized by multiple, often conflicting, criteria. The multicriteria approach can solve complex problems where different aspects must be considered to take the best decision with the available information. Multicriteria methodology has been developed consistently since its beginning that can be identified at the early 1960s. MCDM is a science applied mainly in engineering and business management because it provides analytical tools to address complex problems characterized by multiple evaluation criteria that are often conflicting. A variety of approaches and methods, many implemented by specialized decision-making software, have been developed for their application in an array of disciplines, ranging from politics and business to the environment and energy.

The initial step for the implementation of a MCDM method requires identifying the objective of the choice, criteria and any sub-criteria, and alternatives. Alternatives are the different options or candidates that need to be evaluated. Criteria, on the other hand, are the attributes or factors that are important for making the decision.

Selection of the evaluation criteria

Evaluation criteria must be selected consistently with the objective of the problem. For example, Wang et al. (2009) indicate several criteria and indices for assessing the sustainability of energy systems. At this stage, it is important to identify any correlations or even contrasts between criteria. It is crucial to ensure that the criteria are comprehensive and relevant to the decision at hand. Moreover, double counting should be avoided to minimize redundancies causing biases towards the corresponding criteria. Each criterion should be clearly defined and measurable, whether quantitatively or qualitatively. This step lays the foundation for a structured and objective evaluation process, preparing a transparent basis for decisions. Based on the objective, a skilled decision maker must choose the most appropriate criteria in number and effectiveness. The *Delphi* method can be used to identify these initial criteria. This method involves experts who select the criteria based on debated votes. As more rounds of voting follow, the number of criteria decreases until a limit is reached (e.g., maximum number of rounds, minimum number of criteria, etc.).

Determination of the criteria weights

Once the criteria are defined, a weight must be assigned to each criterion to establish a hierarchy and their relative importance. The weights of criteria significantly influence the decision-making process and require careful consideration of objectivity factors.

Three key characteristics are usually considered to obtain weights: the degree of variability of the criterion, the independence of the criterion, and the subjective preference of the decision-maker. The process of assigning weights often requires input from experts or stakeholders. The sum of all weights should equal 1, ensuring that the total weight is normalized. This normalization is essential to maintain the balance and fairness of the evaluation process.

There are two classes of weighting methods, namely equal weights and ranked weights. The former requires an input of priorities provided by the decision-maker. The second can be subjective, objective, or combined/integrated:

- *Subjective weighting methods:* they rely on the judgment and preferences of decision-makers. These methods are characterized by their flexibility and easiness of use, as they allow decision-makers to directly express their opinions on the relative importance of criteria.
- *Objective weighting methods:* they use mathematical and statistical techniques to determine the weights of criteria based on data. These methods are characterized by their reliance on quantitative information, which makes them less susceptible to personal biases. They provide a more systematic and reproducible approach to weighting.
- *Integrated weighting methods:* they combine both subjective and objective approaches to leverage the strengths of each. These methods aim to balance the intuitive insights of decision-makers with the rigor of data-driven techniques. They are characterized by their ability to provide a more comprehensive and balanced assessment of criteria's weights.

There are several weighting methods applicable to multi-criteria techniques. Most of them are true MCDMs that have a dedicated weighting procedure. As an example, the most common methods are shown in Table 1 elaborated from the works of (Odu, 2019) and (Wang, 2009).

Table 1 Classification of the weighting methods. Elaboration of (Wang et a. 2009) and (Odu et al. 2019).

Subjective weighting methods	Objective weighting methods	Integrated weighting methods
1. Point Allocation	9. Entropy Method	15. Multiplication Synthesis
2. Pairwise Comparison (AHP)	10. Mean Weight	16. Optimal Weighting Based on Sum of Squares
3. Ranking Method	11. Standard Deviation	17. Optimal Weighting Based on Relational Coefficient of Graduation
4. Swing Method	12. Statistical Variance Procedure	
5. Delphi Method	13. CRITIC	
6. SMART	14. TOPSIS	
7. SMARTER		
8. SIMOS		

Determination of alternatives preference order

Once criteria have been defined and weighted, alternatives need to be ordered. The methods that can be used are organized into four categories: elementary, unique synthesizing criteria, outranking, others. For this deliverable, only the second and the third categories will be presented.

- Unique synthesizing criteria
 - Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) calculates the relative importance of alternatives on a ratio scale through the pairwise comparison of evaluation criteria. A matrix is created, and weights are calculated based on the comparisons. It then proceeds with the weighted sum and the best alternative is the one with the highest score.
 - The Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) can be used just as a weighting method, but also as an alternative ranking method. It is based on the concept that the best alternative has the best level for all criteria; instead, the worst alternative has all the worst values in the criteria. This is evaluated by calculating the geometric distance between the alternative and the ideal solution. It belongs to a sub-category named distance-based approaches.
 - Multi-attribute utility theory (MAUT) is particularly useful for solving complex problems that involve both quantitative and qualitative factors. Furthermore, its major advantage is that it allows to consider uncertainties. MAUT is preferred to the usual AHP when the number of alternatives is high, this is perhaps because it avoids the pairwise comparison.
 - Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique (SMART) method is also presented by Wang (2009). Criteria are weighed by a sample of individuals with a scale base of 10 given to the worst criterion, then the scale is normalized on a unitary basis. Later other researchers improved this method by defining the so-called SMARTER method. Agustiawan (2023) proposes an application of this method, but the procedure is completely equivalent to MAUT.

Classical multi criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods assume that all criteria and their respective weights are expressed with defined values. However real cases are dominated by constraints that force imprecision. Another case of information vagueness occurs when the criteria are based on linguistic values rather than numerical ones. MCDM methods that implement this type of treatment are called fuzzy methods.

- Outranking methods
 - ELimination Et Choix Traduisant la REalite (ELECTRE) is a family of outranking methods (OMs) designed by the French school of Roy. Their methodology consists of two main steps: building outranking relations between alternatives and exploiting these relations to obtain the final ranking. Over time, several OMs have been proposed for different and flexible decision-making contexts. The methods differ in how they define the outranking relations and how they apply

these relations to obtain the final ranking. They vary in their approach to manage preferences, weights and the type of outcomes they produce. Some key differences are:

- Type of result: Some methods aim to rank order alternatives, while others sort them into predefined categories.
- Building the outranking relation: Implementing the concordance-discordance principle in various ways, allowing for synergy effects, and using different values of veto and concordance thresholds. Some methods use nested outranking relations or fuzzy outranking relations.
- Comparison on each attribute: Traditional preference models may be inappropriate due to imprecision and uncertainty. Some models involve “weak preference” relations with indifference and/or preference thresholds.

The outranking relation is built through pairwise comparisons of alternatives, using the concordance-discordance principle:

- Concordance condition: many attributes support the assertion that an alternative x is at least as good as y .
- Discordance condition: the opposition from other attributes is not too strong.

After calculating these indices for each pair of alternatives, a graph of weak and strong relations can be drawn to compare these indices with the threshold values. Sometimes ELECTREs are not able to identify the best alternative, but they provide a set of suitable alternatives. Using these methods is very useful when there are few criteria and many alternatives.

ELECTRE methods are the only methods that allow incomparability between two alternatives. One of their drawbacks is that they can take a long time to implement.

ELECTRE I is the oldest and simplest OM. It involves the following steps:

1. Construction of the decision matrix. The process begins with defining the alternatives and the criteria, which are collected into a decision matrix. Each element of the matrix represents the value of alternative with respect to criterion.
2. Normalisation and weighting of criteria. To make the criteria comparable, the decision matrix is normalised. So, weights are assigned to the criteria, reflecting their relative importance. Then, the weighted normalised matrix is obtained by multiplying the normalised values by their respective weights.

3. Calculation of the concordance matrix. The concordance matrix is constructed to measure if one alternative is at least as good as another alternative according to the criteria. The concordance index is the sum of the weights of the criteria when the i -th alternative is equal to or better than the j -th alternative.
4. Calculation of the discordance matrix. The discordance matrix is calculated to evaluate the degree of disagreement between two alternatives. The discordance index represents the maximum difference between the values of the criteria where the j -th alternative outperforms the i -th alternative.
5. Construction of the outranking relation. The concordance and discordance matrices are combined to build an outranking relation. The i -th alternative outranks the j -th alternative if it has a high concordance index and a low discordance index. The purpose is to determine the set of non-dominated alternatives and establish a partial or complete ranking of the alternatives.

Beccali et al. (2003) offer an application case of this technique. The aim of their study is to identify the most suitable energy source to install in Sardinia considering the multiple variables at play (geographical isolation of the region, economic and social development, resources available on site, etc.). The multi-criteria decision method used is ELECTRE III. The method represents the first methodology that is able to implement fuzzy concepts.

- Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment of Evaluations (PROMETHEE) is another method of overcoming that is often used when there are a finite number of alternatives and several, even conflicting, criteria.

3. Methodology

This section describes the methodological approach adopted to prioritize the archetypes in the present deliverable. Specifically, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method has been used. In the next paragraphs, the main rules applied for the purpose are indicated.

3.1 Goal of the Analytic Hierarchy Process analysis

Before beginning the analysis, the NHyRA consortium agreed on the goal of the AHP analysis. Specifically, the analysis must prioritize the archetype to be investigated. Although the AHP analysis can be applied to different purposes of the NHyRA project, it was decided at this stage that the goal of the analysis should focus solely on the prioritization of the archetypes to be tested in order to provide useful recommendations to the Consortium for the selection and the planning of the experimental activities in WP3. However, the results of the analysis will be not mandatory for the realization of the testing that will be finally agreed based also on practical implications that cannot be considered by the proposed qualitative approach.

On the other hand, the results will provide useful information to the entire research community on which archetypes should be prioritized.

3.2 Schematization of the adopted approach

The approach adopted for the prioritization list is shown in Figure 7, which includes five steps to define the priority list of archetypes to be tested. First, the team responsible for the design of the priority list was organized (see section 3.3). Second, the NHyRA-expert team was involved in the identification of the prioritization criteria (see section 3.4). Third, since each criterion has a different importance compared to the others, a weight was assigned. For this purpose, the pair-wise comparison approach based on AHP method has been considered (see section 3.4 and section 3.5). In the fourth step, the same methodology was also adopted to complete the prioritization list of the archetypes to be tested. Finally, a reality check concerning the real capability of respecting the prioritization list was proposed (see section 3.6). It should be noted that, while the implemented approach provides a useful guideline for decision makers on where emissions identification and quantification testing activities should be prioritized and an input for the NHyRA project to select the archetypes to be tested, the final decision will be based on the effective capability of the Consortium.

Figure 7. Approach adopted for the definition of the prioritization list of archetypes to be tested.

3.3 Prioritization team: profile of the participants

For the design of the first version of the priority list, it was agreed to limit the participation to the NHyRA consortium partners. At least one participant from each partner was asked to contribute, resulting in fourteen responses. Six of the responses (i.e., 42.9%) come from industrial partners, while the remaining responses (i.e., 57,1%) were from research institutes and universities. The respondents were only from Europe, i.e., five from Italy (35.71%), two from Germany (14.29%), two from UK (14.29%), one each from France, Spain, Poland, Belgium and Norway (7.14%).

3.4 The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method

AHP consists in the comparison between different alternatives that have to be listed in order of importance. Since a quantitative comparative analysis would be limited by the few data available at the state of the art for the prioritization of archetypes, a qualitative multi criteria approach is considered the best option by the partners for this purpose. Specifically, AHP is a qualitative comparative method and it includes four steps:

1. A hierarchical model is designed to aggregate elements according to their common characteristics at separated levels. The highest level represents the aim of the analysis, the middle one corresponds to the criteria, while the lowest one contains the alternatives to be compared (i.e., the archetypes). A schematic representation of the hierarchical structure is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of the AHP structure applied in the present activity. Figure elaborated from (Pellegrini et al., 2019)

2. In the second step, a pair-wise comparison between elements of the same levels is required based on a specific element of the upper level. A comparative matrix A , in which each element $a_{i,j}$ represents the comparison between the row element a_i and the column element a_j , is designed in accordance with Eq. (1).

$$A = (a_{i,j}) \text{ where } i, j = 1, 2, \dots, \text{number of criteria} \quad (1)$$

Specifically, each element of the matrix has to be compliant with the rules reported in Eq. (2):

$$a_{i,j} > 0; a_{j,i} = \frac{1}{a_{i,j}}; a_{ii} = 1 \quad (2)$$

To assign a value to each element of the matrix, the following question must be answered: “of the two elements, which is more important with respect to the criterion and how much?” This way it is possible to compare two elements respect to a common criterion. For this purpose, a nine points qualitative scale is adopted in accordance with Table 2. If an element has a lower importance, the reciprocal value is used.

Table 2. Relative importance measurement scale.

Greater importance		Lower importance	
Importance intensity	Definition	Weakness intensity	Definition
1	Equal importance	1	Equal weakness
3	Weak importance	1/3	Weak weakness
5	Moderate importance	1/5	Moderate weakness
7	Strong importance	1/7	Strong weakness
9	Extreme importance	1/9	Extreme weakness
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values	1/2, 1/4, 1/6, 1/8	Intermediate values

3. Because of several criteria have been defined for the prioritization of the archetypes, the third step consists in the ranking of criteria and in the evaluation of judgement consistency. For the scope, the principal eigenvector v of the matrix A has to be calculated in accordance with Eq. (3).

$$Av = \lambda_{max}v \quad (3)$$

where λ_{max} is the largest eigenvalue of the matrix A and the corresponding eigenvector v contains only positive entries. The consistency of the matrix is estimated through the calculation of the consistency ratio (CR) as indicated in Eq. (4) as the ratio between the consistency index (CI) and random index (RI).

$$CR = CI/RI \quad (4)$$

CI is calculated in accordance with Eq. (5)

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (5)$$

RI is tabulated as a function of the number of alternatives to be compared (n) as reported in Table 3 Table 3.

Table 3. Random Index. Values taken from (Saaty, 1980).

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

A higher value of the index CR is representative of a poor consistency of the matrix so of the expert judgement. Typically, a threshold value equal to 0.10 can be considered as representative of a good analysis.

4. The last step involves calculating the aggregate priority of each archetype. To calculate the relative weight (RW) for each criterion at each level, Eq. (6) is used:

$$RW = \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{\text{preference of criterion } i \text{ in column } 1}{\text{sum of the entries in column of criteria } 1} + \frac{\text{preference of criterion } i \text{ in column } 2}{\text{sum of the entries in column of criteria } 2} + \dots + \frac{\text{preference of criterion } i \text{ in column } n}{\text{sum of the entries in column of criteria } n} \right] \quad (6)$$

As a result, the final ranking of each archetype can be calculated in accordance with Eq. (7).

$$CW = \sum_{i=1}^n RW_{i,k-1} \times RW_{i,k} \quad (7)$$

Where the subscript k is used to indicate the different level of analysis, i.e., the criteria and the archetypes' levels in the present study.

3.5 Aggregation of the participants' answers

The aggregation of experts' feedback is necessary since the methodology for prioritization is applied to a group of individuals. In this context, different approaches have been evaluated and studied in the literature. Forman and Peniwati (1998), for example, indicated that there are several ways to aggregate answers when more than one participant is involved in the decision process. Specifically, three cases were identified but the Authors focused on i) the aggregation of the individual judgement for each set of pairwise comparison (AIJ) and, ii) the

aggregation of the participants' priorities (AIP). Ossadnik et al. (2016) also investigated the topic of aggregating the participants' answers categorizing the available methodologies. However, even though many methods are available, the Authors investigated only AIJ, AIP, the loss function approach to group aggregation (LFA), and the Group AHP model. For the purpose, the different methods were compared as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Comparative evaluation of the different aggregation techniques based on several evaluation criteria. Source: (Ossadnik et al.,2016).

Evaluation criteria/aggregation techniques	AIJ (WAMM)	AIJ (WGMM)	AIP (WAMM)	AIP (WGMM)	LFA (WAMM)	LFA (WGMM)	Group AHP model
<i>Decision contexts</i>							
Group size: small (~2-5 Persons)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Group size: large (>5 Persons)	•	•	+	+	+	+	+
Situation: common objectives	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Situation: divergent objectives	•	•	+	+	+	+	+
Situation: conflicting objectives	-	-	+	+	•	•	•
<i>Consistency</i>							
Improvement	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
Consideration	-	-	-	-	+	+	-
<i>Social choice axioms</i>							
Universal domain	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Pareto Optimality	•	•	+	+	•	•	•
Independence of irrelevant alternatives	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Non-dictatorship	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Separability condition	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Unanimity condition	•	•	+	+	•	•	•
Homogeneity condition	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
Power conditions (reciprocal property)	-	+	-	+	-	-	-

(+) Satisfied; (•) Partially satisfied/satisfied with restrictions; (-) Not satisfied

Note: AIJ = aggregation of individual judgments; AIP = aggregation of individual priorities; WAMM = weighted arithmetic mean method; WGMM = weighted geometric mean method; LFA = loss function approach to group aggregation.

Because of their complexity, the LFA method and the Group AHP model were excluded. Focusing to the remaining two aggregation techniques, Ossadnik et al. (2016) reported that the AIJ procedure consists in the calculation of the weighted geometric $AIJ_{geometric}(i,j)$ or arithmetic $AIJ_{arithmetic}(i,j)$ mean of the individual judgments for each entry of the pairwise comparison matrices provided by each of the r-th participants (respectively Eq. (8) and in Eq. (9)):

$$AIJ_{arithmetic}(i,j) = \sum_{r=1}^R w^r \times b_{i,j}^r \quad (8)$$

$$AIJ_{geometric}(i,j) = \prod_{r=1}^R (b_{i,j}^r)^{w^r} \quad (9)$$

Where $b_{i,j}^r$ are the individual judgments of the group members, and w^r is the weight of each group member. If different weights would like to be given to participants, the recommendations provided by Forman and Peniwati (1998) should be followed.

The AIP procedure consists in the aggregation of the individual priorities of each participant. As for AIJ, the aggregation can be calculated by means of the arithmetic or geometric mean of the inputs (respectively Eq. (10) and Eq. (11)):

$$AIP_{arithmetic}(i) = \sum_{r=1}^R w^r \times p(B_i)^r \quad (10)$$

$$AIP_{geometric}(i, j) = \prod_{r=1}^R (p^r(B_i))^{w^r} \quad (11)$$

Where $p^r(B_i)$ is the priority for the r-th participant for the alternative B_i .

The selection between AIJ and AIP depends on the specific case, As reported by Forman and Peniwati (1998), AIJ is suggested when the group behaves like a unit while it could be not satisfactory when applied to a group in which each participant behaves as individual.

“When individuals are each acting in his or her own right, with different value systems, we are concerned about each individual’s resulting alternative priorities. An aggregation of each individual’s resulting priorities can be computed using either a geometric or arithmetic mean.”

Since this case applies for this case study, the AIP method was adopted. Furthermore, Ossadnik et al. (2016) indicated:

“Owing to the synergistic character of the AIJ procedure, which treats the group as an individual decision maker, it is only applicable to small groups” (i.e., < 5 participants).

“In situations with divergent or conflicting objectives, the application of the AIJ procedure is quite difficult as the synthesis to collective pairwise comparison matrices is often only accepted by the participants if the group is small and homogenous. However, experts with strong self-interests or manifested personal viewpoints usually do not accept an aggregation of individual judgments to an integrated overall assessment (Saaty 2006). Therefore, in situations with conflicting objectives the AIP procedure which preserves the identification of personal rankings can be seen to be superior towards AIJ”.

Regarding the mathematical form to calculate the aggregation, the geometric mean is considered for the aggregation of the priorities based on the recommendations of Ossadnik et al. (2016):

“The arithmetic form of AIJ (AIJ (WAMM)) generates inconsistent collective pairwise comparison matrices, even if all individual judgments were consistent. This is due to the fact that this kind of arithmetic aggregation

procedure violates the property of reciprocity so that inconsistent matrices arise. In a direct consequence the use of AIJ (WAMM) must generally be excluded for group preference building with AHP and ANP. However, AIJ (WGMM) provides the particular advantage of increasing the consistency for the whole group. Geometric aggregation leads to a compensation of single inconsistent matrices to consistent group judgments”.

“Only the procedure of AIP using the geometric mean is able to satisfy the reciprocal property as special case of the power conditions”.

“Despite of possible inconsistent individual judgments, the geometric aggregation [...] generates a higher or even a complete consistency for the group judgments so that the quality of the decision can be increased. The results of our evaluation imply a particular suitability of the AIP procedure. No other aggregation technique is able to fulfill a comparable number of evaluation criteria. AIP provides a wide range of application possibilities, although the amount of information that is used [...] is quite small, too. Nevertheless, this priority-based aggregation technique can be applied to deal with multi-personal decision-making problems regardless of the group size [...]. Furthermore, AIP shows great potential to support decisions with diverging or conflicting goals. Since AIP (WAMM) cannot guarantee the fulfillment of the power conditions, the AIP (WGMM) is even more suitable in the sense of a rational group decision support”.

3.6 Reality check

A reality check was proposed to allow the NHyRA Consortium in WP3 to select the archetypes to be tested during the project starting from the results of the present study. The partners agreed on defining the procedure for the reality check as shown in Figure 9. It has to be mentioned that the partners identified six prioritization criteria during the task activities (see section 4.1 where the results are shown). After extensive debate, it was agreed to use three of these criteria for the reality check, related to the actual possibility of performing the tests. Specifically, the criteria used for the reality check are related to the capability of the NHyRA Consortium to perform measurements on the prioritized archetypes, the availability of the archetypes to be tested and/or the instruments to be used, the existence of a rigorous methodology, and the available budget and time to complete the testing. More details will be provided during the discussion of the results.

Figure 9. Schematic representation of the final reality check approach. For more details, the readers are invited to read section 4.1 about criteria definition.

Although it was decided not to use the reality check criteria for the prioritization analysis to avoid double counting, the partners agreed to weight these criteria as well. This aims to ensure valuable information for the European Commission and stakeholders on where to focus their efforts to gain additional knowledge about H2 emissions.

3.7 Prioritization of the alternatives: assumptions

The archetypes identified in D1.1 were considered for the prioritization. However, the prioritization was performed in group of the value chain, i.e., maintaining separated the archetypes belonging to production, storage, conversion and reconversion, transport and utilization sections. This approach ensures a larger overview of the value chain.

Some simplifications were assumed to reduce the number of archetypes to be compared. From deliverable D1.1, in fact, 43 potential different archetypes were recognized in the future H2 supply chains. However, the partners agreed to reduce the number of possible alternatives based on the following assumptions:

1. Among the alternatives, archetypes that have currently a low TRL (e.g., TRL6) or that are still far away from real industrial applications should be excluded. Otherwise, the pairwise comparison would be based only on prototype which configurations could be very different from what might eventually enter the market;
2. Archetypes that handle different fluids and which could be responsible only for indirect H2 emissions should be excluded in the prioritization (e.g., NH3, MEOH tanks, etc.);

Figure 10 shows the remaining archetypes to be investigated by AHP. As shown, 21 archetypes remained.

Figure 10. The remaining archetypes to be evaluated by using pairwise comparison.

The following groups were considered:

H₂ production:

- CH₄ steam reforming;
- Coal gasification;
- Water electrolysis;
- Biomass gasification.

H₂ conversion / reversion:

- Compression;
- Liquefaction – regasification;
- LOHC hydrogenation - dehydrogenation;
- NH₃ synthesis – cracking;
- MEOH synthesis – cracking

H₂ transportation:

- Transmission & distribution grids;
- Type III & Type IV CGH₂ tanks;
- LH₂ tanks;

H₂ storage:

- Geological;
- Type I & Type II CGH2 tanks;
- LH2 tanks;

H2 end-uses:

- Industrial;
- Thermal;
- Transport;
- Electricity generation.

During the discussion, it was decided to create two groups for conversion and reconversion. The first group includes archetypes in which H2 does not undergo a chemical reaction and is manipulated as it is (e.g., compression & liquefaction – regasification). The second group includes archetypes in which H2 reacts with other elements to produce another vector that is transported or stored. This choice is justified by the difficulty to make a consistent comparison among the archetypes of the section. Therefore, the following classification was adopted.

H2 conversion / reconversion:

- Compression;
- Liquefaction – regasification;
- LOHC hydrogenation - dehydrogenation;
- NH3 synthesis – cracking;
- MEOH synthesis – cracking

The same approach used for the “conversion/reconversion” sector was also adopted for the archetypes categorized as “end-uses”. In fact, performing pair-wise comparisons among alternatives belonging to different sectors proved challenging and would not contribute to the activities related to scenario development in WP5.

H2 end-uses (industrial):

- Refineries;
- Fertilizers;
- Steel industries.

H2 end-uses for thermal applications:

- Industrial heat;
- Residential heat.

H2 end-uses in mobility:

- Hydrogen Refuelling Stations (HRS) + Fuel cell vehicles;
- Hydrogen Refuelling Stations (HRS) + Internal combustion engine vehicles.

H2 end-uses for energy generation:

- Cogeneration;
- Turbines;
- Fuel cells.

The results of this analysis are provided in section 4.3.

4. Results and discussion

In this chapter the main results of the preliminary prioritization are reported. Specifically, the list of the selected criteria to be considered for the analysis is reported in section 4.1. Then, the ranking of each criterion is discussed in section 4.2. For this purpose, the ranking identified by each partner is firstly reported. Then, the final aggregated ranking is shown. The prioritization of the archetypes based on the inputs from the partners involved in Task 1.3 are shown in section 4.3.

Additional results about individual judgements and the pairwise comparison is reported in the Appendix.

4.1 Identification and definition of the criteria

One of the most crucial steps of the analysis to avoid misunderstanding and rigorous results is the selection of the criteria and their definition. During Task 1.3 activities, in fact, it happened that the same criterion was interpreted differently by the partners. This issue may be due to the multidisciplinary of the group of experts taking part to the Consortium.

In order to enable a common understanding, each criterion was rigorously discussed. A definition was also agreed upon the NHyRA consortium partners of WP1. Even though the Delphi methodology could have been applied to reach consensus among the partners that participated to the selection, it was decided to maintain the discussion open during the periodical WP1 updating meeting.

Partners firstly agreed on the identification of all the potential criteria to be inserted in the analysis at the beginning of the task. UNIBO acted as facilitator to guide the discussion and to facilitate the achievement of a consensus before proceeding in weighting the criteria.

In the first iteration of the process, 11 criteria were identified (i.e., uncertainty about H2 emission, total amount of potential H2 emission, specific H2 emissions (*H2 emissions / amount of conveyed H2*), *market penetration, present and expected future potential, social acceptance/acceptability, know-how of NHyRA Consortium partners / SAB, availability of archetypes to be tested, availability of measuring devices for testing, time required for testing, operational history, variety of scenarios*). Through face-to-face debate during WP1 updating meetings, the partners agreed that some of these criteria were overlapping and/or could be aggregated into a single criterion. Other criteria preliminary included in the list, such as “social acceptance / acceptability” and “specific H2 emissions”, have been omitted because partners agreed that they would not be significant for the specific goal of the AHP.

At the end of the discussion, the partners agreed on proceeding with the following six criteria:

- *Criterion - C1: Existence and/or uncertainty of data about H2 emission in the state of the art*

Definition: It represents the level of availability of data (i.e., the existence of data and/or their uncertainty) about H2 emissions at the state of the art.

This criterion was greatly discussed during the WP1 update meetings. Initially the uncertainty of data was not considered. However, it was deemed necessary to acknowledge that the mere existence of data in the literature is insufficient to define the state of the art. The availability of uncertain data could also be detrimental in evaluating the impact of H2 emissions.

- *Criterion – C2: Total amount of H2 emission*

Definition: Since, few data are available, the total amount of H2 emission is the expected magnitude of H2 emission from the archetype (absolute value).

As with the first criterion, doubts arose regarding the total amount of H2 emissions during the discussion among the partners. Due to the lack of data for several archetypes, this criterion relies on expected and reasonable amount of H2 emission. Based on the inputs during the project and in the future, industrial stakeholders will be able to use more consistent data for prioritization.

- *Criterion – C3: Market penetration (present and future expected potential)*

Definition: It is the expected market penetration of the archetype.

As part of the goal of this project, developing and analyzing comprehensive scenarios of hydrogen releases in the mid-term (2030) and long-term (2050) European hydrogen economy, this parameter plays a crucial role in supporting decision-makers.

A critical aspect of this effort is the identification of key technologies that will shape future hydrogen markets and value chains. Understanding these technologies and their market dynamics is fundamental for constructing scenarios of interest and evaluating their potential environmental impact.

It is hypothesized that the most significant emissions will arise from technologies with the highest market penetration due to the overall emission potential. Therefore, identifying these dominant technologies is essential for implementing scenarios and targeted mitigation strategies.

- *Criterion – C4: Archetype to be tested: availability, operational history and variety of scenarios*

Definition: It is the availability of archetype in NHyRA consortium preferably with extensive operational data on H2 use for comparative assessments, and different operative conditions.

Even if from a measurement perspective it would be important to test as many different types of archetypes as possible, as well as the same archetype on different sites / under different conditions, a choice could be required.

- *Criterion – C5: Availability of measurement instruments and methods*

Definition: It is the availability of measuring devices and validated methods for the measurement of H2 emissions.

Validated measurement-based methods are essential to provide evidences on H2 emissions that can be trusted. The availability of an instrument will be dependent on its technology readiness level, the acceptable trade-off between its performance and the measurement requirements criteria, and its suitability for the intended conditions and environment.

- *Criterion – C6: Cost and time for testing*

Definition: It represents the resources required to complete testing activities for the measurement of the H2 emissions, including costs for logistics of getting the measurement system to the site.

4.2 Weighting of the criteria

As described in the methodology section, the participants were asked to weight the criteria for prioritization. To ensure confidentiality, the results reported in this section are anonymized. The matrices containing the pairwise comparisons of the criteria and the figures showing the relative importance of each criterion compared to the others are reported below for industrial (from Table 5 to Table 10) and research partners (from Table 11 to Table 18). The terms C1-C6 refer to the criteria reported in section 4.1. The calculation sheets implemented in Excel, allowing each partner to check the consistency of its input, are reported in the Appendix. Values reported in the matrices that are between “0” and “1” indicates a weakness of the criterion compared to another or simply lower importance. Values higher than “1” signify a greater importance of the criterion under investigation compared to the criterion reported in the abscissa.

As shown, different opinions appear from the answer of the participants to the survey. However, several rounds were required to ensure a consistency index lower than the threshold limit.

Table 5. Pairwise comparison for industrial partner n°1.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.5	2.0	0.3	1.0	2.0
C2	2.0	1.0	4.0	0.3	2.0	4.0
C3	0.5	0.3	1.0	0.1	0.2	0.3
C4	4.0	3.0	9.0	1.0	2.0	4.0
C5	1.0	0.5	6.0	0.5	1.0	2.0
C6	0.5	0.3	3.0	0.3	0.5	1.0

Table 6. Pairwise comparison for industrial partner n°2.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.5	5.0	0.5	5.0	2.0
C2	2.0	1.0	7.0	1.0	5.0	2.0
C3	0.2	0.1	1.0	0.2	0.3	0.3
C4	2.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	3.0	2.0
C5	0.2	0.2	3.0	0.3	1.0	0.3
C6	0.5	0.5	3.0	0.5	3.0	1.0

Table 7. Pairwise comparison for industrial partner n°3.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	3.0
C2	3.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	6.0
C3	4.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	4.0
C4	5.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	5.0
C5	4.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	4.0
C6	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	1.0

Table 8. Pairwise comparison for industrial partner n° 4.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1
C2	4.0	1.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2
C3	9.0	9.0	1.0	5.0	5.0	3.0
C4	6.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	0.3
C5	6.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	0.3
C6	7.0	5.0	0.3	3.0	3.0	1.0

Table 9. Pairwise comparison for industrial partner n° 5.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.1	3.0	3.0	3.0	5.0
C2	8.0	1.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
C3	0.3	0.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	3.0
C4	0.3	0.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.0
C5	0.3	0.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.0
C6	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	1.0

Table 10. Pairwise comparison for industrial partner n° 6.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.3	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.3
C2	4.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	4.0	0.5
C3	2.0	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	0.3
C4	2.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	2.0	0.3
C5	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.5	1.0	0.3
C6	4.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	1.0

Table 11. Pairwise comparison for research partner n°1.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.3	3.0	4.0	5.0	4.0
C2	3.0	1.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	6.0
C3	0.3	0.2	1.0	4.0	5.0	4.0
C4	0.3	0.2	0.3	1.0	2.0	1.0
C5	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.5
C6	0.3	0.2	0.3	1.0	2.0	1.0

Table 12. Pairwise comparison for research partner n°2.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.3	0.3	5.0	7.1	3.0
C2	3.0	1.0	1.0	7.1	9.1	5.0
C3	3.0	1.0	1.0	7.1	9.1	5.0
C4	0.2	0.1	0.1	1.0	3.0	0.3
C5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	1.0	0.2
C6	0.3	0.2	0.2	3.0	5.0	1.0

Table 13. Pairwise comparison for research partner n°3.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.5	8.0	7.0	8.0	8.0
C2	2.0	1.0	9.0	8.0	9.0	9.0
C3	0.1	0.1	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.3
C4	0.1	0.1	3.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
C5	0.1	0.1	4.0	0.5	1.0	2.0
C6	0.1	0.1	4.0	0.5	0.5	1.0

Table 14. Pairwise comparison for research partner n°4.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	3.0	0.5	2.0	2.0	2.0
C2	0.3	1.0	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.5
C3	2.0	6.0	1.0	5.0	3.0	4.0
C4	0.5	2.0	0.2	1.0	0.5	0.5
C5	0.5	3.0	0.3	2.0	1.0	2.0
C6	0.5	2.0	0.3	2.0	0.5	1.0

Table 15. Pairwise comparison for research partner n°5.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.5
C2	7.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	6.0	7.0
C3	5.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	2.0	1.0
C4	3.0	0.3	0.3	1.0	0.5	2.0
C5	4.0	0.2	0.5	2.0	1.0	1.0
C6	2.0	0.1	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0

Table 16. Pairwise comparison for research partner n°6.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	2.0	4.0	0.1	0.3	0.2
C2	0.5	1.0	2.0	0.1	0.5	0.2
C3	0.3	0.5	1.0	0.1	0.2	0.1
C4	7.0	8.0	9.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
C5	3.0	2.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	2.0
C6	5.0	5.0	7.0	0.5	0.5	1.0

Table 17. Pairwise comparison for research partner n° 7.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	1.0	3.0	0.5	0.3	0.5
C2	1.0	1.0	2.0	0.3	0.3	0.5
C3	0.3	0.5	1.0	0.1	0.1	0.2
C4	2.0	3.0	7.0	1.0	1.0	2.0
C5	3.0	4.0	9.0	1.0	1.0	2.0
C6	2.0	2.0	5.0	0.5	0.5	1.0

Table 18. Pairwise comparison for research partner n° 8.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2
C2	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2
C3	4.0	4.0	1.0	0.2	0.2	0.2
C4	7.0	7.0	6.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
C5	5.0	5.0	5.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
C6	6.0	6.0	5.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

Table 19 shows the ranking calculated from the inputs provided by the industrial partners. As shown, different opinions appear. The most important criterion seems to be criteria C2, i.e., the total amount of H2 emission, even if an industrial partner gave more importance to more practical criteria, e.g., the availability of archetypes to be tested, of instruments and methodology such as resources for performing testing (criteria C4-C6). Proceeding in more detail, industrial partners n° 1 revealed that the criterion C1 has been considered of higher importance with respect to C3 and C6 because having reliable data is a prerequisite for market analysis and determination of costs and timelines. On the other side, C1 is less important than C4 because practical access to operational archetypes for testing is crucial. It is also less important than C2 because the expected absolute magnitude of emissions carries greater weight in guiding priorities. C1 has equal importance as C5 as both are foundational for accurate measurement. Criterion C2 is considered more important than C3, C5 and C6 because the absolute emission quantity is directly tied to environmental impact and decision-making priorities. Otherwise, criterion C2 is less important than C4, as archetypes enable real-world testing and practical insights. Criterion C3 is less important than C4, C5 and C6 because market penetration could play a role in providing directives. However, it is based on predictions which are continuously under variation. Criterion C4 is more important than C3, C5 and C6 because having operational archetypes is

essential for conducting meaningful and reliable tests. Criterion C5 is finally more important than C6 because without adequate measurement tools, tests cannot be performed, regardless of budget or time constraints. Industrial partner n°3 assumed that criterion C3 and criterion C4 more important than criterion C6 regarding resources available for testing. Industrial partner n°5, instead, indicates the amount of H2 emission as the most important criterion for the selection of the archetypes to be tested putting very low importance in all the other. Industrial partner n°6 considers criterion C6 more important than the others, immediately followed by C2 and C3. Criteria C2 and C3 are needed to highlight the archetypes that can both bring a consistent amount of emissions and are well distributed within the market. In addition, the time and cost of the test (C6) is considered to be the key point for the selection of the archetypes in the test phase that realistically quantify the predictability of the emissions. C1 is considered less important, since “uncertainty or availability of data” cannot be taken as a parameter to make an effective activity prioritization.

Table 19. Results provided by industrial partners.

	INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS						GEOM MEAN
	I-1	I-2	I-3	I-4	I-5	I-6	
C1	0.11	0.20	0.07	0.03	0.16	0.07	0.09
C2	0.22	0.29	0.19	0.05	0.59	0.22	0.21
C3	0.04	0.04	0.17	0.45	0.07	0.17	0.11
C4	0.39	0.26	0.29	0.12	0.08	0.13	0.18
C5	0.16	0.07	0.24	0.12	0.08	0.06	0.11
C6	0.08	0.13	0.04	0.23	0.03	0.35	0.10
CI	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.10	0.07	0.04	

Note: Geometric mean is shown in the last column.

The results obtained for criteria C1-C3 were normalized leaving the other three criteria for reality check. Table 20 shows the results. It appears that for 5 partners the H2 emission amount (criterion C2) is the most important. However, there is more disagreement regarding the second most important criterion since 3 partners indicated the lack of information about H2 emission in the state of the art, i.e., the need to investigate to cover the knowledge gap, while 2 partners indicated the importance to dedicate resource and times to those archetypes that are expected to have a greater penetration in the market in medium- and long-term scenarios (criterion C3). Only one partner considered criterion C3 as the most important.

Table 20. Results provided by industrial partners. Normalization of C1-C3 criteria

	INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS						GEOM MEAN
	I-1	I-2	I-3	I-4	I-5	I-6	
C1	0.31	0.38	0.16	0.05	0.20	0.15	0.17
C2	0.59	0.55	0.45	0.09	0.72	0.48	0.41
C3	0.11	0.07	0.39	0.86	0.08	0.37	0.21

Repeating the same exercise for the criteria to be implemented in the reality check, the results are shown in Table 21. Table 21: the most important criterion for 4 partners (66.7%) is criterion C4 (i.e., the availability of the archetypes to be tested), while only two partners indicate the criterion C6 (i.e., resource required in terms of money and time). Interestingly, not all 4 partners that indicated criterion C4 as the most important for reality check agree on the importance of criterion C6. As reported, in fact, 3 of them indicated that the availability of measuring devices and the existence of measurement protocols is more important compared to the resources required.

Table 21. Results provided by industrial partners. Normalization of C4-C6 criteria

	INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS						GEOM MEAN
	I-1	I-2	I-3	I-4	I-5	I-6	
C4	0.62	0.56	0.50	0.26	0.42	0.24	0.41
C5	0.25	0.15	0.42	0.26	0.42	0.11	0.24
C6	0.13	0.29	0.07	0.48	0.17	0.64	0.23

As for industrial partners, divergent opinions were provided also by research partners. The results are shown in Table 22. As shown, 5 partners rely more importance on criteria C1-C3 while the remaining 3 partners put more importance on criteria C4-C6, i.e., related to the reality check.

Research partner n° 1 indicates that criterion C1 is more important than other criteria since it would be a driver towards the selection of the test to be performed. No testing activity or, at least, less urgency will be required for those archetypes for which the literature have already data. Criterion C2 is also considered the other driver for the selection of the archetypes to be tested. Even if in the future, the penetration of the technologies could be different, the selection of the testing activities should be not driven by criterion C3 (i.e., market penetration) since the current technology could be not representative of the one present in the future. Furthermore, criteria C4 and C5 is considered of lower importance. Specifically, for instruments and methods, these should be developed based on the specific requirements. Therefore, should be not considered a hindering limit. As for previous comment, criterion C3 is considered to have a lower importance also compared to C4, C5 and C6.

Research partner n° 2 indicates that criteria C2 and C3 are strongly related to the total amount of actual and expected H2 emissions and, thus, should be prioritized. Among such archetypes, priority should be given to those for which data is missing or uncertain (C1) as NHyRA addresses the knowledge gap regarding the potential amount of the H2 releases expected along the entire H2 value chain. Among these it is reasonable to pick the archetypes which suit the possibilities of the partners in charge of WP3 (criteria C4 and C6). The partner also gave the least priority to C5, as it seems in contrast with both an objective of the project ("WP2 will develop a toolkit of standardized methods for detecting, measuring and quantifying H2 emissions from elements across the entire value chain and WP3 will give experimental support") and with criterion C1 (since

it is likely that, if there is no validated method to evaluate H2 releases for a given archetype, data on emissions will be either lacking or uncertain).

Research partner n°3, instead, identified criterion C2 the most important one followed by criterion C1, while very low or no importance is indicated for market penetration, i.e., criterion C3. The partner also indicated the following order for reality check: C4, C5 and C6.

Research partner n°4 considered criterion C1 the second most important criterion. It provides valuable insights regarding archetypes that require more extensive testing compared to those with more data available in the literature, which consequently have a reduced need to further examination. However, the literature review should first focus on archetypes expected to be widely adopted in the future hydrogen economy. Criterion C2 is considered the least important criterion. The market penetration is seen as more critical because, even if an archetype exhibits high emissions, its overall impact primarily depends on how widespread this technology will be present in the future hydrogen economy. Moreover, priority should be given to archetypes that can be tested or for which emissions can be estimated using available literature and data. Criterion C3 is considered the most important criteria. Priority should be given to archetypes expected to have significant potential in the near future, allow to focus on the most relevant hydrogen technologies that could have the greatest overall impact on H2 emissions, allowing to define effective future hydrogen scenarios. This criterion is seen as more important than C4, C5 and C6, as testing efforts should primarily address technologies that are widespread or likely to become so in the future. Furthermore, C3 is considered more critical than C2, as the overall impact of a single archetype on the H2 emissions depends more in its diffusion and utilization than on the quantity of emissions it produces. Criterion C4 is considered one of the less important criteria. The selection of archetype to be tested should first be based on the expected future penetration of technologies and the data already available in the literature. In addition, before considering the availability of archetype for testing, it is essential to evaluate the availability of measurement instrument, as well as the time and cost involved. Criterion C5 is regarded as the third most important criterion. After identifying the archetypes that are expected to have greater future penetration and those already well documented in the literature, is crucial to evaluate the potential of measuring devices and validated methods for each archetype. Last, criterion C6 is considered less important than criteria C3, C1 and C5, but more important than criteria C4 and C2. The resources required to complete testing activities are regarded as slightly less crucial than the availability of instruments and methods. This is because, even if funding and time are available, validated and reliable methodologies for the measurement of H2 emissions must be established first.

Research partner n°5 scored C2 “total amount of H2 emissions” as the most relevant criterion in the pairwise comparison. This relates to the fact that the potential risk and required mitigation measure strongly depend on the overall emission potential of the H2 emission sources. Thus, C2 was regarded as the first criterion to be considered as priority when selecting archetypes for further testing. Likewise, C3 “future market potential” was regarded as relevant, because the relevance of current archetypes in use can and will change in the future. From emission source perspective, archetypes with a high future market potential, as far as it

can be estimated, should be considered in the experimental testing. C5 “availability of measurement methods” was ranked as third, because it is the prerequisite to finally identify and quantify potential H₂ emissions from the selected archetype. C4 and C5 were less relevant than C2, C3, and C5 and are related to the constraints of the experimental testing, which are still more relevant than C1 “data availability”. The least relevant criterion was C1 “data availability”, because the data would be the result of the experiments of H₂ emissions from potential archetypes and if data would be available no testing is required.

Research partner n°6 considered C4, “Archetype to be tested: availability, operational history, and variety of scenarios,” to be the most important criterion. This is because the availability, operational history, and different scenarios of each archetype must first be identified to establish procedures or address technical aspects of the remaining criteria. C6 and C5 were given almost the same level of priority, as both cost/time and measurement instruments are essential in determining the feasibility of each archetype for H₂ quantification. Furthermore, C1, “Uncertainty,” was ranked higher than C2, “Total amount of H₂ emission,” since the uncertainty of the methods and data must be assessed before estimating H₂ emissions. For instance, the data directory for failure frequency in H₂ equipment is not yet fully developed. The available data is based on predicted failure frequencies using Bayesian calculations, making data uncertainty a factor that needs to be anticipated. Lastly, C3, which pertains to market penetration, was considered the least important. While market volatility may delay the adoption of H₂ as an energy source, this should not pose a significant issue once the technology is proven and feasible. Moreover, there is strong confidence that H₂ will eventually replace conventional fuels to support the transition to clean energy.

Research partner n°7 indicated that criterion C1 was less important than criteria C4 to C6, because if it is possible to carry out measurements within the project, the available literature data lose their importance. However, criterion C1 was considered more important than C2 and C3, because the availability of data on estimated emissions is a basic data for the inventory. Criterion C2 was considered to be of little importance, because the total emission from a given type of source is composed of two factors: the emission amount per single source and the number of sources of a given type. Having only data on total emission, it is difficult to determine the nature of the emission source. Criterion C3 was considered the least important. Market penetration does not have to be correlated with the volume of hydrogen emissions. Criterion C4 was considered one of the most important criteria. The availability of archetypes for tests and the possibility of testing different scenarios is crucial for the development of measurement methods. Conducting measurements on different types of archetypes, in different operating conditions will allow for obtaining reliable data for inventory. Criterion C5 was considered the most important (slightly more than C4). Since the methods of measuring hydrogen emissions are in the development phase, this may be a more significant limitation in the possibility of obtaining measurement data than the availability of archetypes for tests. Criterion C6, as a criterion related to the possibility of conducting measurements, was considered more important than criteria C1 to C3. At the same time, Criterion C4 was considered less important than the remaining criteria

related to the possibility of conducting measurements (C5-C6), because the resources for conducting tests should be diversified.

Last, research partner n°8 justified its input in the following manner. First of all, it has been assumed that current data on the existence or uncertainty of about H2 emissions is based on predictions (and not based on validated measurement methods) and therefore should exercise caution on the reliability of this data for the selection of archetypes to test. Similarly, for C2. Therefore, C1 and C2 should have a low prioritisation compared to C3 to C6. Therefore, market penetration (C3) is considered to have a higher importance than C1 and C2 but less than C4 and C6. Expected market penetration should provide some weighting on the direction so that relevant archetypes are tested, but the partner assumes this is based on current predictions / expectations, so may change in the future. Criterion C4 (Archetype to be tested: availability, operational history and variety of scenarios) is considered the one with the highest importance. The performance and applicability (i.e., its scope) of a measurement method will be dependent on the conditions and the particular scenario being tested. Therefore, from a method development perspective it is important to test methods under a variety of scenarios and conditions, so that its scope can be properly assessed. Operation history (and current operating conditions) is valuable information too. A slightly lower priority (compared to C4), although important is the availability of validated methods and instruments such that the research community and all the interested stakeholders have data that can be trusted and understand the limitations of instruments.

As it has been done for industrial partners, criteria C1-C3 were normalized to obtain first indication for the archetype prioritization. The same method was applied also to criteria C4-C6. Results are reported in Table 23 and Table 24, respectively. As shown, 4 partners (50%) considered criterion C2 the most important, while the other four partners were evenly divided (25% each) between the remaining two criteria. By calculating the geometric mean, a weak indication of the higher importance of C2 is present, while no difference can be assumed between C1 and C3. Focusing to criteria C4-C6, there is less variability in the inputs provided by the research partners, as indicated by the geometric mean. After performing the aggregation, a weak importance of criterion C4 seems to present while the difference between criterion C6 and C5 is considered very small.

Table 22. Results provided by research partners.

	RESEARCH PARTNERS								GEOM MEAN
	R-1	R-2	R-3	R-4	R-5	R-6	R-7	R-8	
C1	0.23	0.17	0.33	0.20	0.04	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.12
C2	0.44	0.34	0.45	0.06	0.40	0.06	0.09	0.04	0.15
C3	0.16	0.34	0.03	0.40	0.23	0.03	0.04	0.09	0.11
C4	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.40	0.28	0.30	0.13
C5	0.04	0.03	0.07	0.15	0.12	0.21	0.32	0.26	0.11
C6	0.06	0.09	0.05	0.11	0.10	0.22	0.17	0.27	0.12
CI	0.07	0.05	0.09	0.02	0.10	0.07	0.01	0.06	

Note: Geometric mean is shown in the last columns.

Table 23. Results provided by research partners.

	RESEARCH PARTNERS								GEOM MEAN
	R-1	R-2	R-3	R-4	R-5	R-6	R-7	R-8	
C1	0.28	0.20	0.41	0.31	0.06	0.47	0.46	0.23	0.26
C2	0.53	0.40	0.56	0.08	0.60	0.34	0.38	0.23	0.34
C3	0.20	0.40	0.04	0.61	0.34	0.19	0.16	0.53	0.24

Note: Geometric mean is shown in the last column.

Table 24. Results provided by research partners.

	RESEARCH PARTNERS								GEOM MEAN
	R-1	R-2	R-3	R-4	R-5	R-6	R-7	R-8	
C4	0.38	0.29	0.38	0.24	0.31	0.48	0.36	0.36	0.34
C5	0.24	0.16	0.34	0.44	0.37	0.25	0.42	0.31	0.30
C6	0.38	0.55	0.28	0.32	0.31	0.27	0.22	0.33	0.32

Note: Geometric mean is shown in the last two column.

The final aggregation of the inputs provided by industrial and research partners is shown in Table 25Table 25.

Table 25. Aggregation of all provided inputs by industrial and research partners.

	INDUSTRIAL (I) AND RESEARCH (R) PARTNERS														GEOM MEAN	GEOM MEAN*
	I-1	I-2	I-3	I-4	I-5	I-6	R-1	R-2	R-3	R-4	R-5	R-6	R-7	R-8		
C1	0.11	0.20	0.07	0.03	0.16	0.07	0.23	0.17	0.33	0.20	0.04	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.103	0.14
C2	0.22	0.29	0.19	0.05	0.59	0.22	0.44	0.34	0.45	0.06	0.40	0.06	0.09	0.04	0.175	0.23
C3	0.04	0.04	0.17	0.45	0.07	0.17	0.16	0.34	0.03	0.40	0.23	0.03	0.04	0.09	0.106	0.14
C4	0.39	0.26	0.29	0.12	0.08	0.13	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.40	0.28	0.30	0.147	0.20
C5	0.16	0.07	0.24	0.12	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.07	0.15	0.12	0.21	0.32	0.26	0.109	0.15
C6	0.08	0.13	0.04	0.23	0.03	0.35	0.06	0.09	0.05	0.11	0.10	0.22	0.17	0.27	0.110	0.15

(*) The sum of the values obtained from the geometric mean could be different from 1. This behaviour is different respect the arithmetic mean. Therefore, a normalization is necessary to obtain a sum equal to 1.

Limiting to criteria C1-C3, the final weight indicated in Table 26 Table 26 were calculated. Regarding the reality check, the final ranking is reported in Table 27 Table 27.

Table 26. Final weights of the criteria adopted for the prioritization of the archetypes.

WEIGHT	
C1	0.269
C2	0.455
C3	0.276

Table 27. Final weights of the criteria adopted for the reality check.

	WEIGHT	ORDER OF IMPORTANCE
C4	0.402	1°
C5	0.298	3°
C6	0.300	2°

4.3 Identification of the archetypes to be prioritized

The final ranking obtained for the H2 value chain sections are reported below.

Hydrogen production

Table 28 Table 28 shows the final ranking for H2 production. The first row indicates the weight of the three criteria indicated in the previous paragraph (Table 26 Table 26). As shown, the greatest priority was given to Steam Methane Reforming (SMR), followed by electrolysis, biomass gasification and coal gasification. The result can be explained as follow. Considering criterion C1, SMR is the most critical technology impacted by the lack of data, as it is currently and will likely remain in the near future the primary source of hydrogen production. However, it must be noted that potential H2 emissions are mainly due to loss of tightness in the plant while vented emissions are usually flared (hot) resulting in no direct H2 emission into the atmosphere. Furthermore, SMR operators carefully maintain and inspect the plant to minimize these emissions since they would result in a loss of revenues. Missing data for coal and biomass gasification carry greater weight than for electrolysis, due to the increased complexity of measurement tests (e.g., space requirements, operational conditions). Moreover, the focus on electrolysis technology has grown significantly in recent years, resulting in an ever-increasing amount of available data (a trend expected to continue in the future). By considering criterion C2, on the other hand, partners agreed that SMR should have the greatest ranking since steam methane reforming plant, due to their capacity, are potentially characterized by high H2 emission (total value). Therefore, even if specific H2 emission (i.e., the ratio of H2 emission divided by the total production) could be the lowest, since SMR has the greatest penetration in H2 production, the partners agreed to give it priority in order to confirm real H2 emissions. Electrolysers, biomass and coal gasification plants follow SMR. Moving to

market penetration, the partners agreed on giving electrolysers the greatest priority. Indeed, European strategy plans to install a large nominal capacity of electrolysis plants in next years. However, to cover future demand, SMR plants is expected to continue its operation in short and medium term even if proper carbon capture utilization and storage (CCUS) solutions will be applied to reduce CO2 emissions in the atmosphere. Biomass and coal gasification, otherwise, will have a different penetration in the market. While biomass gasification could play a minor role ensure the production of renewable H2, availability of biomass and its reasonable logistics will represent a limit in its deployment in the future. Coal gasification, on the other, is expected to have the lowest penetration (Europe) due to the abandonment of this fossil fuel even if CCUS solutions could reduce the environmental impact. The values indicated for the pairwise comparison is reported in the Appendix.

Table 28. Final ranking for archetypes in the H2 production sector.

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	-
CH4 SMR	0.49	0.50	0.28	0.435
COAL GASIFICATION	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.099
ELECTROLYSIS	0.08	0.27	0.49	0.277
BIOMASS GASIFICATION	0.28	0.15	0.15	0.188

Hydrogen conversion

As indicated in section 3.7, the comparison has been performed among:

- Archetypes in which H2 simply changes its thermodynamic operating condition: Compression vs liquefaction;
- Archetypes in which H2 is transformed into another fluid:

Regarding the first comparison (compression vs liquefaction), the partner adopted the following assumptions to fill in Table 29:

- Data uncertainty about H2 emissions considered equivalent for both compression and liquefaction service since components and equipment installed are equivalent.

- H2 volume in installed compression plants are larger than those typical in liquefaction service.

Based on these assumptions, compression appears to be more relevant respect to liquefaction in the assessment of H2 emissions.

Table 29. Final ranking between compression and liquefaction.

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	-
COMPRESSION	0.50	0.83	0.83	0.744
LIQUEFACTION	0.50	0.17	0.17	0.256

Regarding the second comparison, Table 30 shows the results. The partners agree to the fact that LOHC hydrogenation is a low priority due to the expected future market outlook and available projects (mainly: large mass/storage capacity handling required, significant heat integration at harbour site required for plausible economics). For MeOH Synthesis and NH3 synthesis, a slightly higher priority should be given to the carbon free NH3 option based on the fact that ammonia is also the more plausible route as H2 carrier without having the requirement for a closed CO2 cycle. However, it has to be kept in mind that the H2 provision e.g., via electrolysis, could be in principle the same for both processes and that the main differences are the synthesis loop and MeOH purification vs. Ammonia liquefaction.

Table 30. Final ranking among LOHC hydrogenation, ammonia and MeOH synthesis.

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	
LOHC HYDROGENATION	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.071
AMMONIA SYNTHESIS	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.511
MEOH SYNTHESIS	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.418

Hydrogen transport

Based on the inputs received, transmission and distribution pipelines resulted the highest archetype of the hydrogen transport to be prioritized (Table 30). Specifically, the most energy efficient transport in pipelines achieves the greatest ranking in all the defined criteria. The partners agreed that due to their expected length and the amount of hydrogen transported is reasonable to assume that this element of the supply chain has the highest importance for the total H2 emissions, followed by liquid hydrogen tanks and compressed H2 tanks. Market penetration also seems to favour transport in pipelines respect in trucks. The large amount of hydrogen that is expected in the future, in fact, would require a dedicated infrastructure that is not compatible with the nominal capacity of a liquid or gas hydrogen transport by truck. Finally, although few information is available for the amount of the emissions occurring when hydrogen is transported by truck, more uncertainties is still present for the pipeline systems. For example, pipeline systems include next to the compression and let down stations several components (flanges, valves, fittings, pipe) in different configurations that are still far away to be mapped in terms of emissions in real operating conditions.

Table 31. Final ranking for archetypes in the H2 transportation sector.

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	-
T & D PIPELINES	0.62	0.76	0.63	0.689
BY CG_H2 TANKS	0.16	0.07	0.11	0.103
BY L_H2 TANKS	0.22	0.17	0.26	0.208

Hydrogen storage

Compared to the previous section, less difference appears between archetypes in hydrogen storage (Table 32). However, geological storage is considered the most important priority for investigation. Looking at each criterion, few data about H2 emissions from geological sites are available. At the same time, the state-of-the-art includes data about potential emissions from compressed and liquid H2 tanks, as indicated in D1.1. Regarding total H2 emissions, the analysis resulted in more complicated results, and it is based on reasonable assumptions based on the fact that geological storage is assumed to be characterized by storage capacity much larger than the other two solutions. Last, compressed storage tanks are assumed to be the solution with the highest market penetration thanks to their easiness of implementation both from a technical and authorization point of view and economic feasibility, especially for small capacity needs. Similarly, liquid hydrogen tanks could be favoured in the long term, considering the development of the transport of liquid H2 between long distances by ships. As shown in D1.1, examples of bigger liquid tanks are under construction worldwide. A different scenario is expected for geological storage, where long times are usually required to complete the project, starting from the selection of the site, the approval of the authoritative procedures, and the design of the storage.

Table 32. Final ranking for archetypes in the H2 storage sector.

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	-
GEOLOGICAL	0.72	0.54	0.12	0.474
CG H2 TANKS	0.08	0.16	0.56	0.250
LH2 TANKS	0.19	0.30	0.32	0.276

Hydrogen end uses

The analysis of hydrogen end-users' archetypes resulted more challenging compared to other sections of the supply chain and an agreement was not reached for some of the investigated sections (industrial and energy production). The partners agree that a more in-depth analysis would be needed before proposing a ranking list.

Regarding H2 mobility (Table 33), instead, fuel cell based market was considered to have a greater priority for H2 emissions than a mobility based on internal combustion engine (ICE). This result is explained as follows. First, the literature includes data about H2 emissions from flue gases of ICE engines while data for fuel cells mostly refer to safety considerations due to extreme events. Regarding criterion C2, no significant difference was assumed for the two technologies. On the other hand, fuel cell mobility was assumed to have a greater market penetration compared to ICE technology in the future.

Table 33. Final ranking for archetypes in the H2 end uses (mobility).

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	-
HRS + FUEL CELL	0.80	0.50	0.89	0.688
HRS + ICE	0.20	0.50	0.11	0.312

Heat production

The results for heat production were reported in Table 34. As shown, a greater priority was calculated for industrial heat. This conclusion can be explained by the following reasons. While the available know-how about H2 emissions can be considered the same for the two technologies, a higher value for industrial applications is expected for criterion C2 since larger emissions are expected compared to residential applications. The same vision is also assumed for criterion C3. In fact, since heat demand is usually limited to low temperature, technologies for heat electrification could be responsible for a lower market penetration of residential heat respect to industrial applications.

Table 3435. Final ranking for archetypes in the H2 end uses (heat production).

	C1	C2	C3	FINAL RANKING
CRITERIA WEIGHT	0.27	0.46	0.28	-
INDUSTRIAL HEAT	0.50	0.58	0.90	0.648
RESIDENTIAL HEAT	0.50	0.42	0.10	0.352

5. Conclusions, limits of the study and recommendations for the future activities

This report presents the preliminary prioritization of H₂ supply chain archetypes as part of Task 1.3 of the NHyRA project. Given the complexity of the hydrogen value chain, a multicriteria decision-making approach was adopted to assess the most relevant archetypes based on a predefined set of criteria.

The study employs the **Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)** methodology to rank archetypes based on six predefined criteria, including uncertainty in emission data, total emissions, and market penetration.

The study categorizes the hydrogen value chain into **production, conversion/reconversion, transportation, storage, and end-use** sectors. Each sector's key archetypes were assessed through expert discussions and a structured decision-making process. A preliminary ranking of archetypes was established, providing insights into which elements of the H₂ value chain should be prioritized for future investigation and testing. As already indicated by Copper et al. (2022), a further understanding of H₂ emission is necessary to cover the existing gaps. Furthermore, the investigation should be prioritized based on several criteria that include the current research community knowledge, the total amount of H₂ archetype emissions and the expected market penetration.

The preliminary results provided in this report reflect only the opinions of the experts involved in the NHyRA Consortium. This may be a limitation of the analysis. Therefore, additional inputs from external stakeholders, i.e., the SAB, would be welcomed to ensure a broader point of view. However, the current approach, involving iterative and face-to-face discussion, represents a limit when several participants are included in the prioritization team. Therefore, before proceeding to inviting other participants, alternative methods for gathering inputs should be considered to avoid misleading results or challenges in aggregating different opinions. In fact, as shown in this report, different rankings among partners may lead to a flattening of the aggregated results. Nevertheless, according to the rules agreed upon with the members of the NHyRA Consortium, this preliminary ranking should be shared for review to the Advisory Board members.

Second, the criteria ranking should be repeated at the end of the project since more knowledge about H₂ emissions is expected to emerge in the state of the art reducing the necessity to invest resources in the investigation of specific archetypes. On the other hand, new criteria may be required based on new needs or other considerations that could arise during the progress of the project.

Third, although the reduction of archetypes described in previous section is a limitation of the study, the NHyRA consortium agrees to investigate also the importance of discarded archetypes based on low TRL during SAB events. This will provide useful indications to the decision makers in the final prioritization list. In fact, while low TRL technologies could be investigated from an industrial point of view, feedback from the manufacturers would be encouraged through dissemination and communication activities.

Fourth, the comparison of separated value chain steps is another limitation of the approach applied. In fact, while this allows to prioritize each value chain process step it does not provide a general overview, i.e., to identify the potentially most “emitting” archetype of the entire value chain. The applied methodology would be

very limited in comparing several archetypes with different purposes. For example, the ranking provided for the end uses is only preliminary and more discussion within the NHyRA consortium and external members of the Advisory Board is needed to consider all the potential aspects that could influence the final results as at the end of the project.

The present methodology will definitely contribute to provide recommendations to cover the knowledge gap indicated by Copper et al. (2022), i.e., *“more data on emissions and losses is desperately needed for all stages of the H2 supply chain, specifically direct measurement data”*.

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Appendix

The pairwise comparison matrices – Industrial partners

The calculation of the weight was performed in excel by each partner. To calculate the maximum eigenvalues as required by the AHP model, the Power Method was implemented in the excel sheet. To validate the excel file, eigenvalues where also checked by using the Matlab software.

A caption of the sheet obtained for each partner is shown below.

Industrial partner n° 1

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking	V	Random Index	1.24
C1	1	0.5	2	0.25	1	2	0.114	1	λ_{max}	6.2431
C2	2	1	4	0.3333	2	4	0.2167	1	n	6
C3	0.5	0.25	1	0.1111	0.1667	0.3333	0.0394	1	Consistency Index (CI)	0.04862
C4	4	3	9	1	2	4	0.3932	1	Consistency target	PASSED
C5	1	0.5	6	0.5	1	2	0.1578	1	Consistency ratio (CR)	0.039
C6	0.5	0.25	3	0.25	0.5	1	0.0789	1		

k	$V^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	6.75	13.33	2.36	23.00	11.00	5.50	23.00	-	-	-
1	0.29	0.58	0.10	1.00	0.48	0.24	2.00	3.82	0.66	6.75	2.66	1.33	6.75	16.25000	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.30	0.57	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.81	3.46	0.63	6.34	2.46	1.23	6.34	0.40790	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.19	1.78	3.40	0.62	6.22	2.43	1.21	6.22	0.11690	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.01650	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00410	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00080	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2429
8	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.2431
9	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.243
10	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2431
11	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.243
12	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2431
13	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.243
14	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2431
15	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.243
16	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2431
17	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.243
18	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2431
19	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.243
20	0.29	0.55	0.10	1.00	0.39	0.20	1.79	3.41	0.62	6.24	2.44	1.22	6.24	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2431

Industrial partner n° 2

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking	V	Random Index	1.24
C1	1	0.5	5	0.5	5	2	0.203	1	λ_{max}	6.2235
C2	2	1	7	1	5	2	0.2937	1	n	6
C3	0.20	0.14	1	0.2	0.3333	0.3333	0.0396	1	Consistency Index (CI)	0.0447
C4	2.00	1.00	5.00	1	3	2	0.2606	1	Consistency target	PASSED
C5	0.20	0.20	3.00	0.33	1	0.3333	0.069	1	Consistency ratio (CR)	0.036
C6	0.50	0.50	3.00	0.50	3.00	1	0.1341	1		

k	$V^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	14.00	18.00	2.21	14.00	5.07	8.50	18.00	-	-	-
1	0.78	1.00	0.12	0.78	0.28	0.47	4.63	6.54	0.83	5.74	1.42	2.96	6.54	11.45560	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.71	1.00	0.13	0.88	0.22	0.45	4.27	6.17	0.81	5.48	1.38	2.78	6.17	0.37480	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.22	0.45	4.31	6.21	0.81	5.50	1.40	2.81	6.21	0.04150	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.33	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.01380	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00100	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00040	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2234
8	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2235
9	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
10	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
11	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
12	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
13	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
14	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
15	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
16	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
17	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
18	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235
19	0.69	1.00	0.13	0.89	0.23	0.45	4.32	6.22	0.82	5.51	1.40	2.81	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2235

Industrial partner n° 3

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking							V	Random Index	
C1	1	0.3333	0.25	0.2	0.25	3	0.0681							1	1.24	
C2	3	1	1	0.5	1	6	0.1944							1	λ _{max}	6.2144
C3	4	1	1	0.5	0.5	4	0.1687							1	n	6
C4	5	2	2	1	1	5	0.2869							1	Consistency Index (CI)	0.04288
C5	4	1	2	1	1	4	0.2397							1	Consistency target	PASSED
C6	0.3333	0.1667	0.25	0.2	0.25	1	0.0421							1	Consistency ratio (CR)	0.035

k	V ^(k)						AV ^(k)						m _{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ _{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	5.03	12.50	11.00	16.00	13.00	2.20	16.000		-	
1	0.31	0.78	0.69	1.00	0.81	0.14	1.56	4.55	4.18	7.01	5.78	0.95	7.010	8.98960	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.22	0.65	0.60	1.00	0.82	0.14	1.40	4.05	3.59	6.11	5.10	0.87	6.106	0.90450	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.23	0.66	0.59	1.00	0.84	0.14	1.43	4.13	3.66	6.20	5.16	0.89	6.199	0.09260	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.22	5.18	0.89	6.218	0.01960	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.215	0.00330	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00050	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2142
8	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2143
9	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2144
10	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2143
11	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2142
12	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2143
13	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2144
14	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2143
15	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2142
16	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2143
17	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2144
18	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2143
19	0.23	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.83	0.14	1.44	4.14	3.67	6.21	5.17	0.89	6.214	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2142

Industrial partner n° 4

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking							V	Random Index	
C1	1	0.25	0.1111	0.1667	0.1667	0.1429	0.0263							1	1.24	
C2	4	1	0.1111	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0494							1	λ _{max}	6.4858
C3	9	9	1	5	5	3	0.4507							1	n	6
C4	6	5	0.2	1	1	0.3333	0.1236							1	Consistency Index (CI)	0.09716
C5	6	5	0.2	1	1	0.3333	0.1236							1	Consistency target	PASSED
C6	7	5	0.3333	3	3	1	0.2265							1	Consistency ratio (CR)	0.078

k	V ^(k)						AV ^(k)						m _{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ _{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.84	5.71	32.00	13.53	13.53	19.33	32.00		-	
1	0.06	0.18	1.00	0.42	0.42	0.60	0.44	0.81	9.16	2.48	2.48	4.77	9.16	22.83540	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.05	0.09	1.00	0.27	0.27	0.52	0.35	0.60	6.50	1.65	1.65	3.26	6.50	2.66570	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.05	0.09	1.00	0.25	0.25	0.50	0.34	0.62	6.35	1.66	1.66	3.19	6.35	0.14760	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.48	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.48	0.12920	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.50	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.50	0.01520	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00930	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00130	NOT REACHED	-
8	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00060	NOT REACHED	-
9	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
10	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
11	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
12	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
13	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
14	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
15	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
16	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
17	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
18	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
19	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
20	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
21	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
22	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
23	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856
24	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4858
25	0.05	0.10	1.00	0.26	0.26	0.50	0.35	0.63	6.49	1.70	1.70	3.27	6.49	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.4856

Industrial partner n° 5

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking		V		Random Index	1.24
C1	1.00	0.13	3.00	3.00	3.00	5.00	0.15985		1		λ_{max}	6.3627
C2	8.00	1.00	9.00	9.00	9.00	9.00	0.58915		1		n	6
C3	0.33	0.11	1.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	0.0692		1		Consistency Index (CI)	0.07254
C4	0.33	0.11	1.00	1.00	1.00	4.00	0.07561		1		Consistency target	PASSED
C5	0.33	0.11	1.00	1.00	1.00	4.00	0.07561		1		Consistency ratio (CR)	0.059
C6	0.20	0.11	0.33	0.25	0.25	1.00	0.03057		1			

k	$V^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	15.13	45.00	6.44	7.44	7.44	2.14	45.000	-	-	
1	0.34	1.00	0.14	0.17	0.17	0.05	2.12	8.38	0.84	0.89	0.89	0.36	8.384	36.61560	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.04	1.53	6.21	0.64	0.68	0.68	0.29	6.215	2.16960	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.57	6.27	0.65	0.70	0.70	0.30	6.268	0.05290	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.37	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.371	0.10360	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.37	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.368	0.00310	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.362	0.00630	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.362	0.00040	NOT REACHED	-
8	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
9	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3625
10	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.3627
11	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3626
12	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3625
13	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.3627
14	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3626
15	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3625
16	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.3627
17	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3626
18	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3625
19	0.25	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.05	1.59	6.36	0.66	0.71	0.71	0.30	6.363	0.00020	CONVERGED	6.3627

Industrial partner n° 6

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking		V		Random Index	1.24
C1	1	0.25	0.50	0.50	1	0.25	0.0682		1		λ_{max}	6.2185
C2	4	1	2	1	4	0.5	0.2207		1		n	6
C3	2	0.5	1	2	4	0.3333	0.1678		1		Consistency Index (CI)	0.0437
C4	2	1	0.5	1	2	0.33	0.1311		1		Consistency target	PASSED
C5	1	0.25	0.25	0.5	1	0.25	0.0624		1		Consistency ratio (CR)	0.035
C6	4	2.00	3.00	3	4	1	0.3499		1			

k	$V^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	3.50	12.50	9.83	6.83	3.25	17.00	17.00	-	-	
1	0.21	0.74	0.58	0.40	0.19	1.00	1.32	4.38	3.26	2.55	1.18	7.00	7.00	10.00000	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.36	0.17	1.00	1.18	3.85	2.89	2.27	1.06	6.17	6.17	0.82910	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.19	0.62	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.88	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.21	6.21	0.03880	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00960	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00070	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2184
8	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2184
9	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2185
10	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2184
11	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2185
12	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2184
13	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2185
14	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2184
15	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2185
16	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2184
17	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2185
18	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2184
19	0.19	0.63	0.47	0.37	0.17	1.00	1.19	3.89	2.92	2.29	1.07	6.22	6.22	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2185

The pairwise comparison matrices – Research partners

As performed for industrial partners, a caption of the sheet obtained for each research partner is shown below.

Research partner n° 1

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking		V		Random Index	1.24
C1	1	0.3333	3	4	5	4	0.231		1		λ_{max}	6.3292
C2	3	1	5	6	7	6	0.4424		1		n	6
C3	0.33	0.20	1.00	4.00	5.00	4	0.1635		1		Consistency Index (CI)	0.06584
C4	0.25	0.17	0.25	1.00	2.00	1	0.0618		1		Consistency target	PASSED
C5	0.20	0.14	0.20	0.50	1.00	0.5	0.0396		1		Consistency ratio (CR)	0.053
C6	0.25	0.17	0.25	1.00	2.00	1	0.0618		1			

k	$V^{(k)}$							$AV^{(k)}$							m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	17.33	28.00	14.53	4.67	2.54	4.67	28.00		-			
1	0.62	1.00	0.52	0.17	0.09	0.17	4.30	8.09	2.71	0.97	0.63	0.97	8.09	19.91130	NOT REACHED	-		
2	0.53	1.00	0.34	0.12	0.08	0.12	3.21	6.25	2.06	0.78	0.51	0.78	6.25	1.84020	NOT REACHED	-		
3	0.51	1.00	0.33	0.12	0.08	0.12	3.24	6.26	2.11	0.79	0.52	0.79	6.26	0.00970	NOT REACHED	-		
4	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.29	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.07620	NOT REACHED	-		
5	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00100	NOT REACHED	-		
6	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00380	NOT REACHED	-		
7	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		
8	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3292		
9	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		
10	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3292		
11	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		
12	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3292		
13	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		
14	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3292		
15	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		
16	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3292		
17	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		
18	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3292		
19	0.52	1.00	0.34	0.13	0.08	0.13	3.28	6.33	2.13	0.80	0.52	0.80	6.33	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3291		

Research partner n° 2

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking		V		Random Index	1.24
C1	1	0.3333	0.3333	5	7.1429	3.0303	0.1663		1		λ_{max}	6.2749
C2	3	1	1	7.1429	9.0909	5	0.3367		1		n	6
C3	3	1	1	7.1429	9.0909	5	0.3367		1		Consistency Index (CI)	0.05498
C4	0.2	0.14	0.14	1	3	0.3333	0.0466		1		Consistency target	PASSED
C5	0.14	0.11	0.11	0.33	1	0.2	0.0257		1		Consistency ratio (CR)	0.044
C6	0.33	0.2	0.2	3.00	5	1	0.088		1			

k	$V^{(k)}$							$AV^{(k)}$							m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	16.84	26.23	26.23	4.81	1.89	9.73	26.23		-			
1	0.64	1.00	1.00	0.18	0.07	0.37	3.87	7.75	7.75	0.93	0.52	1.89	7.75	18.48690	NOT REACHED	-		
2	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.12	0.07	0.24	2.99	6.19	6.19	0.78	0.45	1.50	6.19	1.56110	NOT REACHED	-		
3	0.48	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.24	3.03	6.22	6.22	0.80	0.45	1.54	6.22	0.03550	NOT REACHED	-		
4	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.07	6.28	6.28	0.81	0.45	1.56	6.28	0.05700	NOT REACHED	-		
5	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.28	6.28	0.81	0.45	1.56	6.28	0.00100	NOT REACHED	-		
6	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00250	NOT REACHED	-		
7	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2748		
8	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2749		
9	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2748		
10	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2749		
11	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2748		
12	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2749		
13	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2748		
14	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2749		
15	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2748		
16	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2749		
17	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2748		
18	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2749		
19	0.49	1.00	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.25	3.06	6.27	6.27	0.80	0.45	1.55	6.27	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2748		

Research partner n° 3

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking	V					Random Index		λ _{max}
C1	1	0.5	8	7	8	8	0.3274	1							1.24
C2	2	1	9	8	9	9	0.4482	1							6.4616
C3	0.13	0.11	1	0.3333	0.25	0.25	0.0282	1							6
C4	0.14	0.13	3	1	2	2	0.0753	1							0.09232
C5	0.13	0.11	4	0.50	1	2	0.0662	1							PASSED
C6	0.13	0.11	4	0.50	0.50	1	0.0547	1							0.074

k	V ^{(k)T}						AV ^{(k)T}						m _{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ _{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	32.50	38.00	2.07	8.27	7.74	6.24	38.000		-	
1	0.86	1.00	0.05	0.22	0.20	0.16	6.26	8.25	0.44	1.36	1.08	0.81	8.251	29.74950	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.76	1.00	0.05	0.17	0.13	0.10	4.67	6.37	0.37	1.01	0.83	0.66	6.373	1.87710	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.73	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.10	4.68	6.37	0.37	1.03	0.85	0.68	6.368	0.00500	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.77	6.47	0.38	1.05	0.87	0.69	6.466	0.03780	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.77	6.47	0.38	1.05	0.87	0.69	6.468	0.00180	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00650	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.461	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
8	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
9	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4616
10	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4616
11	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4615
12	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4616
13	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4616
14	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4615
15	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4616
16	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4616
17	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4615
18	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4616
19	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4616
20	0.74	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.11	4.76	6.46	0.38	1.05	0.86	0.69	6.462	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.4615

Research partner n° 4

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking	V					Random Index		λ _{max}
C1	1.00	3.00	0.50	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.2032	1							1.24
C2	0.33	1.00	0.17	0.50	0.33	0.50	0.0552	1							6.1207
C3	2.00	6.00	1.00	5.00	3.03	4.00	0.3978	1							6
C4	0.50	2.00	0.20	1.00	0.50	0.50	0.0835	1							0.02414
C5	0.50	3.00	0.33	2.00	1.00	2.00	0.1518	1							PASSED
C6	0.50	2.00	0.25	2.00	0.50	1.00	0.1085	1							0.019

k	V ^{(k)T}						AV ^{(k)T}						m _{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ _{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	10.50	2.83	21.03	4.70	8.83	6.25	21.030		-	
1	0.50	0.13	1.00	0.22	0.42	0.30	3.28	0.87	6.39	1.30	2.45	1.72	6.385	14.64490	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.20	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.10	1.26	2.33	1.65	6.103	0.28240	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.65	6.118	0.01500	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00290	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
7	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207
8	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
9	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207
10	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
11	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207
12	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
13	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207
14	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
15	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207
16	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
17	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207
18	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1206
19	0.51	0.14	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.27	3.14	0.84	6.12	1.26	2.33	1.66	6.121	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.1207

Research partner n° 5

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking	V						Random Index	
C1	1	0.1429	0.2	0.3333	0.25	0.5	0.0403	1							1.24
C2	7	1	1	4	6	7	0.4039	1							6.4817
C3	5	1	1	3	2	1	0.2314	1							6
C4	3	0.25	0.33	1	0.5	2	0.1017	1							0.09634
C5	4	0.17	0.50	2	1	1	0.1208	1							PASSED
C6	2	0.14	1	0.50	1	1	0.1018	1							0.078

k	$V^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.43	26.00	13.00	7.08	8.67	5.64	26.000	-	-	-
1	0.09	1.00	0.50	0.27	0.33	0.22	0.62	6.76	3.67	1.57	1.89	1.52	6.762	19.23780	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.09	1.00	0.54	0.23	0.28	0.22	0.60	6.35	3.48	1.53	1.77	1.49	6.354	0.40860	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.12860	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.54	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.484	0.00220	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.481	0.00310	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
8	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
9	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
10	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
11	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
12	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
13	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
14	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
15	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
16	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
17	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
18	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817
19	0.09	1.00	0.55	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.61	6.48	3.53	1.56	1.81	1.51	6.482	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.4817

Research partner n° 6

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking	V						Random Index	
C1	1	2	4	0.1429	0.3333	0.2	0.0801	1							1.24
C2	0.50	1	2	0.125	0.5	0.2	0.059	1							6.3496
C3	0.25	0.50	1	0.1111	0.2	0.1429	0.0324	1							6
C4	7.00	8.00	9.00	1	2	2	0.399	1							0.06992
C5	3.00	2.00	5.00	0.50	1	2	0.2096	1							PASSED
C6	5.00	5.00	7.00	0.50	0.50	1	0.2199	1							0.056

k	$V^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{k+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	7.68	4.33	2.20	29.00	13.50	19.00	29.000	-	-	-
1	0.26	0.15	0.08	1.00	0.47	0.66	1.30	0.92	0.51	6.97	3.75	3.99	6.971	22.02860	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.19	0.13	0.07	1.00	0.54	0.57	1.18	0.88	0.49	6.24	3.37	3.45	6.244	0.72760	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.54	0.55	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.34	3.39	3.52	6.341	0.09760	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.354	0.01280	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00420	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.349	0.00060	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
8	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
9	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
10	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
11	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.3496
12	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
13	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
14	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
15	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
16	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
17	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
18	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496
19	0.19	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.53	0.56	1.22	0.90	0.49	6.35	3.39	3.53	6.350	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.3496

Research partner n° 7

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking							V	Random Index	
C1	1	1.00	3.03	0.50	0.33	0.50	0.1058							1	1.24	6.0464
C2	1.00	1.00	2.00	0.33	0.25	0.50	0.0872							1		
C3	0.33	0.50	1.00	0.14	0.11	0.20	0.0373							1		
C4	2.00	3.00	7.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	0.2762							1	0.00928	PASSED
C5	3.00	4.00	9.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	0.3209							1		
C6	2.00	2.00	5.00	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.1725							1		0.007

k	$v^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{L+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	6.36	5.08	2.28	16.00	20.00	11.00	20.000		-	
1	0.32	0.25	0.11	0.80	1.00	0.55	1.93	1.59	0.68	5.10	5.90	3.17	5.899	14.10100	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.63	0.70	5.21	6.04	3.24	6.037	0.13820	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.047	0.00960	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.047	0.00030	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00020	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0463
7	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.0464
8	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
9	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
10	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
11	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
12	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
13	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
14	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
15	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
16	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
17	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
18	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464
19	0.33	0.27	0.12	0.86	1.00	0.54	1.98	1.64	0.70	5.22	6.05	3.25	6.046	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.0464

Research partner n° 8

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	Ranking							V	Random Index	
C1	1	1	0.25	0.14285714	0.2	0.16666667	0.0403							1	1.24	6.2947
C2	1	1	0.25	0.14285714	0.2	0.16666667	0.0403							1		
C3	4	4	1	0.16666667	0.2	0.2	0.0918							1	0.05894	PASSED
C4	7	7	6	1	1	1	0.2961							1		
C5	5	5	5	1	1	1	0.2588							1		
C6	6	6	5	1	1	1	0.2727							1		0.048

k	$v^{(k)}$						$AV^{(k)}$						m_{L+1}	e	Iteration - Convergence	λ_{max}
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.76	2.76	9.57	23.00	18.00	20.00	23.000		-	
1	0.12	0.12	0.42	1.00	0.78	0.87	0.79	0.79	1.87	6.83	5.93	6.17	6.828	16.17250	NOT REACHED	-
2	0.12	0.12	0.27	1.00	0.87	0.90	0.77	0.77	1.72	6.03	5.30	5.53	6.035	0.79260	NOT REACHED	-
3	0.13	0.13	0.28	1.00	0.88	0.92	0.80	0.80	1.83	6.28	5.49	5.74	6.282	0.24720	NOT REACHED	-
4	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.83	6.31	5.51	5.76	6.308	0.02560	NOT REACHED	-
5	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.79	0.79	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.294	0.01330	NOT REACHED	-
6	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.79	0.79	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.294	0.00050	NOT REACHED	-
7	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00070	NOT REACHED	-
8	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00010	CONVERGED	6.2947
9	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
10	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
11	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
12	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
13	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
14	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
15	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
16	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
17	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
18	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947
19	0.13	0.13	0.29	1.00	0.87	0.91	0.80	0.80	1.82	6.29	5.50	5.75	6.295	0.00000	CONVERGED	6.2947

The pairwise comparison matrices – H2 production

The pairwise comparison for all the archetypes in H2 production for the three criteria C1, C2 and C3 are shown in the following figure. As for previous cases, the calculation of the maximum eigenvalue was performed in excel and validated in Matlab.

MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS						V	Random Index	
CH4 SMR	COAL GASIFICATION	ELECTROLYSIS	BIOMASS GASIFICATION	Ranking	λmax		Consistency ratio (CR)	
CH4 SMR	1.00	3.00	6.00	2.00	0.49	1	0.9	
COAL GASIFICATION	0.33	1.00	2.00	0.50	0.15	1	4.0104	
ELECTROLYSIS	0.17	0.50	1.00	0.25	0.08	1	n	
BIOMASS GASIFICATION	0.50	2.00	4.00	1.00	0.28	1	Consistency Index (CI)	
							0.003	
							Consistency target	
							PASSED	
							Consistency ratio (CR)	
							0.004	

TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS						V	Random Index	
CH4 SMR	COAL GASIFICATION	ELECTROLYSIS	BIOMASS GASIFICATION	Ranking	λmax		Consistency ratio (CR)	
CH4 SMR	1.00	6.00	2.00	3.00	0.50	1	0.9	
COAL GASIFICATION	0.17	1.00	0.33	0.50	0.08	1	4.0104	
ELECTROLYSIS	0.50	3.00	1.00	2.00	0.27	1	n	
BIOMASS GASIFICATION	0.33	2.00	0.50	1.00	0.15	1	Consistency Index (CI)	
							0.0035	
							Consistency target	
							PASSED	
							Consistency ratio (CR)	
							0.004	

MARKET PENETRATION						V	Random Index	
CH4 SMR	COAL GASIFICATION	ELECTROLYSIS	BIOMASS GASIFICATION	Ranking	λmax		Consistency ratio (CR)	
CH4 SMR	1.00	4.00	0.50	2.00	0.28	1	0.9	
COAL GASIFICATION	0.25	1.00	0.17	0.50	0.08	1	4.0104	
ELECTROLYSIS	2.00	6.00	1.00	3.00	0.49	1	n	
BIOMASS GASIFICATION	0.50	2.00	0.33	1.00	0.15	1	Consistency Index (CI)	
							0.003466667	
							Consistency target	
							PASSED	
							Consistency ratio (CR)	
							0.004	

Figure 11. The pairwise comparison of the four archetypes of H2 production for the three selected criteria.

The pairwise comparison matrices – H2 transportation

The pairwise comparison for all the archetypes in H2 transportation for the three criteria C1, C2 and C3 are shown in the following figure. As for previous cases, the calculation of the maximum eigenvalue was performed in excel and validated in Matlab.

MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS					V	Random Index	
Transmission & Distribution	by CGH2 Tanks	by LH2 Tanks	Ranking	λmax		Consistency ratio (CR)	
Transmission & Distribution	1.00	3.00	4.00	0.620	0	0.58	
by CGH2 Tanks	0.33	1.00	0.50	0.156	1	3.1079	
by LH2 Tanks	0.25	2.00	1.00	0.224	0	n	
						3	
						Consistency Index (CI)	
						0.05395	
						Consistency target	
						PASSED	
						Consistency ratio (CR)	
						0.093	

TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS					V	Random Index	
Transmission & Distribution	by CGH2 Tanks	by LH2 Tanks	Ranking	λmax		Consistency ratio (CR)	
Transmission & Distribution	1.00	9.00	6.00	0.764	0	0.58	
by CGH2 Tanks	0.11	1.00	0.33	0.070	1	3.0537	
by LH2 Tanks	0.17	3.00	1.00	0.166	0	n	
						3	
						Consistency Index (CI)	
						0.02685	
						Consistency target	
						PASSED	
						Consistency ratio (CR)	
						0.046	

MARKET PENETRATION					V	Random Index	
Transmission & Distribution	by CGH2 Tanks	by LH2 Tanks	Ranking	λmax		Consistency ratio (CR)	
Transmission & Distribution	1.00	5.00	3.00	0.633	0	0.58	
by CGH2 Tanks	0.20	1.00	0.33	0.106	1	3.0386	
by LH2 Tanks	0.33	3.00	1.00	0.260	0	n	
						3	
						Consistency Index (CI)	
						0.0193	
						Consistency target	
						PASSED	
						Consistency ratio (CR)	
						0.033	

Figure 12. The pairwise comparison of the archetypes of H2 transportation for the three selected criteria.

The pairwise comparison matrices – H2 storage

The pairwise comparison for all the archetypes in H2 storage for the three criteria C1, C2 and C3 are shown in the following figure. As for previous cases, the calculation of the maximum eigenvalue was performed in excel and validated in Matlab.

MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS					V	Random Index	
Geological	CG H2 Tanks	LH2 Tanks	Ranking	0		0.58	
Geological	1.00	7.00	5.00	0.724	0	λ_{max}	3.065
CG H2 Tanks	0.14	1.00	0.33	0.083	1	n	3
LH2 Tanks	0.20	3.00	1.00	0.193	0	Consistency Index (CI)	0.0325
						Consistency target	PASSED
						Consistency ratio (CR)	0.056

TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS					V	Random Index	
Geological	CG H2 Tanks	LH2 Tanks	Ranking	0		0.58	
Geological	1.00	3.00	2.00	0.539	0	λ_{max}	3.0093
CG H2 Tanks	0.33	1.00	0.50	0.164	1	n	3
LH2 Tanks	0.50	2.00	1.00	0.297	0	Consistency Index (CI)	0.00465
						Consistency target	PASSED
						Consistency ratio (CR)	0.008

MARKET PENETRATION					V	Random Index	
Geological	CG H2 Tanks	LH2 Tanks	Ranking	0		0.58	
Geological	1.00	0.25	0.33	0.123	0	λ_{max}	3.0199
CG H2 Tanks	4.00	1.00	2.00	0.557	1	n	3
LH2 Tanks	3.00	0.50	1.00	0.320	0	Consistency Index (CI)	0.00995
						Consistency target	PASSED
						Consistency ratio (CR)	0.017

Figure 13. The pairwise comparison of the archetypes of H2 storage for the three selected criteria.

The pairwise comparison matrices – H2 conversion

The pairwise comparison for all the archetypes in H2 conversion for the three criteria C1, C2 and C3 are shown in the following figures. Figure 14 shows the comparison between compression and liquefaction, while Figure 15 shows the comparison among archetypes that do not simply involve a change of state of hydrogen but a conversion in another chemical.

MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS			
	COMPRESSION	LIQUEFACTION	Ranking
COMPRESSION	1,00	1,00	0,5
LIQUEFACTION	1,00	1,00	0,5

TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS			
	COMPRESSION	LIQUEFACTION	Ranking
COMPRESSION	1,00	5,00	0,833333
LIQUEFACTION	0,20	1,00	0,166667

MARKET PENETRATION			
	COMPRESSION	LIQUEFACTION	Ranking
COMPRESSION	1,00	5,00	0,833333
LIQUEFACTION	0,20	1,00	0,166667

Figure 14. The pairwise comparison of between compression and liquefaction.

MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS					V		
LOHC Hydrogenation	NH3 Synthesis	MeOH Synthesis	Ranking			Random Index	0,58
LOHC Hydrogenation	1,00	0,14	0,17	0,071	0	λ_{max}	3,0006
NH3 Synthesis	7,00	1,00	1,25	0,511	1	n	3
MeOH Synthesis	6,00	0,80	1,00	0,418	0	Consistency Index (CI)	0,0003
						Consistency target	PASSED
						Consistency ratio (CR)	0,001

TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS					V		
LOHC Hydrogenation	NH3 Synthesis	MeOH Synthesis	Ranking			Random Index	0,58
LOHC Hydrogenation	1,00	0,14	0,17	0,071	0	λ_{max}	3,0006
NH3 Synthesis	7,00	1,00	1,25	0,511	1	n	3
MeOH Synthesis	6,00	0,80	1,00	0,418	0	Consistency Index (CI)	0,0003
						Consistency target	PASSED
						Consistency ratio (CR)	0,001

MARKET PENETRATION					V		
LOHC Hydrogenation	NH3 Synthesis	MeOH Synthesis	Ranking			Random Index	0,58
LOHC Hydrogenation	1,00	0,14	0,17	0,071	0	λ_{max}	3,0006
NH3 Synthesis	7,00	1,00	1,25	0,511	1	n	3
MeOH Synthesis	6,00	0,80	1,00	0,418	0	Consistency Index (CI)	0,0003
						Consistency target	PASSED
						Consistency ratio (CR)	0,001

Figure 15. The pairwise comparison among LOHC hydrogenation, NH3 synthesis, MeOH synthesis.

The pairwise comparison matrices – H2 end uses

MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS			
	HRS + FUEL CELL	HRS + ICE	Ranking
HRS + FUEL CELL	1,00	4,00	0,80
HRS + ICE	0,25	1,00	0,20

TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS			
	HRS + FUEL CELL	HRS + ICE	Ranking
HRS + FUEL CELL	1,00	4,00	0,80
HRS + ICE	0,25	1,00	0,20

MARKET PENETRATION			
	HRS + FUEL CELL	HRS + ICE	Ranking
HRS + FUEL CELL	1,00	8,00	0,84
HRS + ICE	0,13	1,00	0,11

Figure 16. The pairwise comparison of the H2 end uses (mobility) for the three selected criteria.

	MISSING AND/OR UNCERTAINTY OF DATA ABOUT H2 EMISSIONS		
	Industrial heat	Residential heat	Ranking
Industrial heat	1.00	5.00	0.83
Residential heat	0.20	1.00	0.17

	TOTAL AMOUNT OF H2 EMISSIONS		
	Industrial heat	Residential heat	Ranking
Industrial heat	1.00	0.50	0.33
Residential heat	2.00	1.00	0.67

	MARKET PENETRATION		
	Industrial heat	Residential heat	Ranking
Industrial heat	1.00	9.00	0.62
Residential heat	0.11	1.00	0.10

Figure 17. The pairwise comparison of the H2 end uses (heat production) for the three selected criteria.